

VideoScribe Insight: Solution for Students?

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Abstract— This project aims to develop a comprehensive system for extracting and summarizing information from audio frames through automated transcription. The process involves utilizing Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) technology to convert spoken words into text, followed by advanced natural language processing (NLP) techniques for information extraction. The extracted information is then summarized using either extractive or abstractive summarization methods. The project encompasses data collection, annotation, and iterative refinement to optimize system performance.

Keywords— Image Recognition, Text summarization, NLP, ASR

I. INTRODUCTION

The project VideoScribe Insight is a vision of every student who self-studies. The project takes the core problem of the learner to captivate itself on the video subject for the duration of that video lecture. The issue is not regarding the quality of video rather the length of the video. To the students who are just on the verge of exams they have lost the golden time to study, they rather have the notes for the course than having to watch a lecture that spans an hour or two.

It poses problem for the students to get the summarised notes for the video subject. Now there are two ways you can tackle the issue to provide the summarised notes for the video lecture:

1. Audio transcription and summarization 2.Extracting the video frames for the subject

The issue with each of those methods is the ambiguity they pose, if you rely simply on audio transcription the teacher may use vague, ambiguous statements or may repeat some statements in many forms.

This makes it harder for the students to understand a single topic as it may be taught in some contradictory statements.

To tackle this issue, we propose our project VideoScribe Insight which helps the student's, researchers, and scientists

to get the brief knowledge about the topic.

The project poses a solution by integrating 3 modules which would result in better accuracy for the given subject. As we shed some lights on the issues, we integrate audio transcription with image recognizer for recognizing text from the video. By their integration we get ample amount of information. The issue persists for ambiguity for larger the data, larger the ambiguity.

For that we integrate a summarizing module to tackle the foretold ambiguity and provide a well- structured note for further learning.

The goal of the VideoScribe Insight project is to develop a system that can analyse videos comprehensively using techniques such as frame analysis, audio transcription, and summarization.

The following paper showcases the research done to bring the project to reality.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. User Interface:

Design a user-friendly interface allowing users to input text documents.

Provide options for users to select summarization techniques (e.g., extractive, or abstractive) and set summary length preferences.

Figure 1: Workflow of System

B. Audio/Audit Transcription:

The extracted features are then processed by a speech recognition system, which matches patterns in the audio

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signal to phonemes (the smallest units of sound in a language) and words. This involves using statistical models, machine learning algorithms, or deep learning models trained on large datasets of labelled audio recordings and corresponding transcriptions.

C. Frame Analyzer:

Frame generation from a video involves extracting individual frames from the video content. This process is commonly used in computer vision, video processing, and machine learning applications.

Frame captioning is a computer vision task that involves generating descriptive textual captions for frame. The goal is to develop algorithms or models capable of understanding the content of a frame and expressing it in natural language.

D. Summarization Module:

Choose and implement a summarization algorithm based on project requirements (e.g., TF-IDF, Text Rank, BERT). Develop logic to score and rank sentences or phrases based on their relevance and importance within the text.

The Advantages it brings on table:

Enhanced Comprehension: By generating concise summaries of lengthy texts, the system helps users quickly grasp key information, improving comprehension and reducing the time needed to digest large volumes of text.

Time Efficiency: The automated summarization process saves time compared to manually reading and summarizing texts, making it particularly useful for busy professionals, researchers, and students who need to review large amounts of information efficiently.

Improved Accessibility: The summarizer increases the accessibility of information by providing condensed summaries that are easier to read and understand, catering to users with limited time or attention spans.

Consistency and Objectivity: The system generates summaries in a consistent manner, avoiding biases or subjective interpretations that may arise from manual summarization. This promotes objectivity and reliability in the summarization process.

Scalability: The automated nature of the system allows it to handle large volumes of text efficiently, making it scalable for processing extensive documents or datasets without compromising performance.

Error Reduction: By automating the summarization process, the system reduces the likelihood of human errors that may occur during manual summarization, ensuring greater accuracy and reliability of the generated summaries.

III. SYSTEM USED BEHIND

A. Frame Analyzer:

For analysis of the video for the text present in it, we would need to generate stills or image of a particular frame (Frame extraction).

We would need to use OpenCV, short for Open-Source Computer Vision Library, is an open-beginning calculating fantasy and machine intelligence program library. It can process representations and videos to recognize objects, faces, or even the handwriting of a human. When it is joined accompanying differing athenaeums, in the way that NumPy that is a very improved bibliotheca for numerical movements, before the number of armaments increases in your Arsenal anything movements individual be able in NumPy can be linked accompanying OpenCV.

OpenCV comes with a function for capturing the video frames using `video_capture()`, and reads them by using `read()`.

The module gets the frames as an input to extract text from. We tried using tesseract which is used to extract text from images and documents without a text layer and outputs the document into a new searchable text file, PDF, or most other popular formats, but in our trials to extract texts through frames, the tesseract model showed relatively poor accuracy. We mostly received incomplete texts, omitted letters, it would often replace letters with special symbols. We pre-processed the images for better compatibility and extraction of texts, but the results were underwhelming.

Figure 2: The original image we feed to the tesseract.

Figure 2: The text we received.

The above results showcase the worst possible scenario where we can see all the issues:

- Omitted Letters
- Interchange of letters and symbols
- Incomplete Sentence
- Cannot recognize the objects in background.

Due to underwhelming results that cannot cater to the purpose of our project we tried alternatives, but we could not find any viable and better alternates so to counter above mentioned issues we train a machine learning model to recognize objects and text residing in the image.

The training for the model is done using Google Colab and TensorFlow KERAS for the portability between the teammates. It provides us with cloud computing and provides us with Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) powerful enough to handle the training of the machine learning model.

IV. MACHINE LEARNING MODEL

A. Training Setup:

The code aims to train a machine learning model.

It specifies the number of epochs (complete passes through the dataset) as 20.

The batch size is set to 32, which determines how many data samples are processed together during each training step.

B. Data Generator:

A data generator is used to efficiently load and preprocess data during training.

The data_generator function in our code prepares the data for training.

Parameters passed to the generator include information about the training dataset, features, tokenization, and vocabulary size.

C. Model Training:

• The model.fit method trains the machine learning model.

• It runs for one epoch (as specified by epochs=1).

• The steps_per_epoch parameter determines the number of training steps per epoch.

• The verbose=1 setting prints training progress during each step.

D. Overall Loop:

The outer for loop iterates over the specified number of epochs (20).

Inside the loop, the model is trained using the data generator.

With the model trained we tackled the above- mentioned issues

- Omitted Letters.
- Interchange of letters and symbols.
- Incomplete Sentence.
- Cannot recognize the objects in background.

The model can now predict what is being enacted in the video frame.

The model was fed with the image below and was expected to return some situation it can suggest by analyzing this image.

Here actual scenario includes.

Figure 3: black dog and spotted dog are fighting

- Start-seq black dog and spotted dog are fighting end-seq
- Start-seq black dog and tri-coloured dog playing with each other on the road end-seq
- Start-seq black dog and white dog with brown spots are staring at each other in the street end-seq
- Start-seq two dogs of different breeds looking at each other on the road end-seq
- Start-seq two dogs on pavement moving toward each other end-seq And the output the model generated “Start-seq two dogs play with each other in the grass end-seq”

Where the tesseract showed only approximately 14.29%. This means that only about 14.29% of the recognized characters match the original sentence. The accuracy of the model’s output compared to the actual scenarios is approximately 63.84%.

The Whisperer

The Whisperer is an audio transcription module we will be using a speech recognition model made by OpenAI to use it to generate captions for a given video. The whisperer or whisper is joined by other open- source speech-to-text models available today - like Kaldi, Vosk, wav2vec 2.0, and others - and matches state-of-the-art results for speech recognition. To use Whisper, we require Python version 3.7 or above and a recent version of PyTorch and an audio-processing library FFmpeg.

The model also supports languages other than English, but the WER is comparatively high, and the performance is comparatively lacking for other languages.

Below we see the distribution of languages as a function of word error rate. Of the 82 languages in the plot above, 50 of them have Word-Error-Rates greater than 20%.

Figure 4: Whisperer distribution of languages

The below figure from the Whisper paper compares Whisper's accuracy, using Word-Error-Rate (WER), to current state-of-the-art speech recognition models. As you can see, Whisper reports achieving state-of-the-art results, which is an exciting development for the field of speech recognition, especially given that Whisper is an open-source model. By implementing this model in our project, we ensure maximum accuracy for extracting accurate text from the video file. By captioning the speaker or the speakers. We now have information from both audio of the video and the frames of the video in next module we would be compiling the extracted information and generate a summarized note.

Figure 5: The chart represents the WER comparing whisper with other models available today

3. THE SUMMARIZER

Text summarization plays a crucial role in condensing

large volumes of information into concise and coherent summaries, facilitating efficient comprehension and knowledge extraction. With the advent of advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, particularly leveraging pre-trained language models, the field has witnessed significant advancements.

Summarization can be:

- Extractive: extract the most relevant information from a document.
- Abstractive: generate new text that captures the most relevant information.

Hugging Face API

Hugging Face offers a comprehensive suite of tools and resources for NLP model development and deployment. The Hugging Face API provides access to a wide range of pre-trained models, including state-of-the-art architectures like BERT, GPT, and T5 (Text-To-Text Transfer Transformer). Developers can leverage these models for tasks such as text classification, question answering, and, importantly, text summarization. The Hugging Face API provides a RESTful interface that allows users to interact with the hosted models seamlessly. Users can make HTTP requests to the API endpoint, passing input text or data, and receive predictions or outputs in return. This interface abstracts away the complexities of model easy integration into applications and workflows.

When a request is made to the Hugging Face API, the input text is tokenized based on the model's tokenizer. Tokenization involves breaking down the input text into smaller units, such as words or sub- words, which are then mapped to numerical representations suitable for processing by the model. The tokenized input is fed into the pre-trained model, which performs inference to generate predictions or outputs based on the input. Once the model completes the inference process, the API returns the results to the user in a structured format, typically JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) or plain text. For tasks like text summarization, the response might include the generated summary or summaries, along with additional information such as confidence scores or metadata.

By integrating the Hugging Face API in our project, we condense the bulky data extracted from previous two models. The data will be cleaned, and any redundancy will be cleared out, bringing homogeneity to the data. The data will be paraphrased to match the requirements of the person, that would enable him/her to properly understand the context of the video.

To integrate the API of Hugging face we use flask, a micro web framework because it does not require tools or libraries for python. It is used to integrate pre- existing third-party libraries provides same functions API.

CONCLUSION

In this project, we aim to develop a robust frame generation system capable of extracting individual frames from video

content. The key objectives are to decode video files, extract frames at a specified frame rate, and store them for further analysis. The project leverages the OpenCV library in Python to implement these tasks efficiently.

We Aim to Achieve:

1. **Frame Extraction Process:** We must develop and implement a reliable frame extraction process, ensuring that frames were accurately captured at the specified frame rate.
2. **Code Efficiency:** The use of OpenCV will contribute to the efficiency of the frame extraction process, making the project suitable for processing large video datasets.
3. **Flexibility:** The project provides flexibility for future applications by allowing users to adjust frame rates, preprocessing steps, and storage formats based on their specific needs.

The Challenges we face:

1. **Computational Resources:** The efficiency of the frame extraction process is subject to the computational resources available. In cases of extremely large video files or real-time applications, further optimization may be necessary.
2. **Metadata Handling:** While frame extraction focused on the visual content, incorporating more metadata about each frame, such as timestamps or

frame numbers, could enhance the utility of the generated frames.

In conclusion, the frame generation system presented in this project successfully addresses the primary objectives of extracting frames from video content. While achievements are notable, there are opportunities for further optimization and expansion to enhance the system's capabilities for real-world applications. Overall, this project would provide a solid foundation for future developments in video processing and computer vision tasks.

FUTURE SCOPE

A. Assistive Technology

The project could be expanded further in future to work as an assistive technology for people who lack vision (blind) by integrating a text-to-speech module in addition with the current modules enabling the project to generate voice for the events happening on screen. Better Accuracy

In future the accuracy of the model can be further improved, thus increasing reliability and possible integration in our day to day lives.

B. Next-gen Translator

With current translators being only limited to texts we could expand our project by incorporating multiple languages thanks to the capabilities of summarizer being honed continuously.

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